

IMPACT OF PIGMENTS ON THE HEALTH OF *Punica Granatum L.*

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ABSTRACT. The pomegranate, scientifically known as *Punica granatum L.*, is an intriguing fruit due to its nutritional makeup, which includes a high chlorophyll concentration, flavor, and cultural importance. Chlorophyll levels in leaves ensure that the plant can efficiently produce carbohydrates that can be transported to developing fruits. Also, a decrease in chlorophyll levels can directly affect the growth of pomegranate due to a reduced photosynthetic rate. In this research effect of the content of leaf pigments on different varieties (Healthy and Cracked fruits) of pomegranate from the same cultivar, Bhagwa, was determined. Two distinct seasons were selected for sample collection, one with the initial developing stage of fruits and the second where fruits were in the harvest stage. The analysis revealed that leaf pigment levels at the initial development stage were almost identical in healthy and cracked fruit. Still, as the development of fruit starts, and when it reaches the fully developed stage, the pigment levels in all extracting solvents in leaves of the plant-bearing cracked fruit decreased when compared with healthy fruit. So, parameters leading to a decrease in chlorophyll content need to be evaluated, and protection methods should be implemented at appropriate times to reduce cracking and overall growth of pomegranate.

Keywords: *Punica granatum L.*, Cracking, Chlorophyll, Carotenoids.

INTRODUCTION

Punica granatum L. (Pomegranate), native to the Punicaceae family, is a small tree that originated from Iran to the Himalayas of India [1]. As a nutritious fruit, pomegranate has quickly gained its importance. As the chemical variation in fruit during its maturation stage affects its nutrition level and health, it is vital to harvest pomegranate at the stage where it has the highest latent health-enhancing components [2]. Fruit cracking is a severe problem that badly affects the production and quality of pomegranate [3]. The market cost then falls, and regularly, instances turn unhealthy for human intake [4,5]. Cracking of pomegranate fruit is a typical hassle in its developing areas and among all types worldwide. Still, the magnitude of the trouble relies upon weather, heredity, nutrient deficiency, variety, fruit growth, and cultural practice [6]. Photosynthesis is the native process of any substance and energy flow in nature. The chlorophyll-protein complex absorbs the energy of sunlight, after which it is transmitted as excitation energy to the response core of photosystems (PS II and PS I) in the light-dependent phase of photosynthesis [7].

As chlorophyll is an essential sign of chloroplast level, regular estimation of photosynthetic mechanism and plant metabolism is necessary at regular intervals. Chlorophyll is deposited in the chloroplast of green leaves, stems, flowers, and roots and is found to be an antioxidant compound [8-9]. In plant photosystems, chlorophyll a and b play a vital role [10]. Energy in plants is produced with the help of chlorophyll a. Moreover, the level of chlorophyll a is two

to three-fold higher in comparison with chlorophyll b. [8] The salt effects on the chlorophyll concentration of leaves depend mainly on genotype, species, salt concentration, and plant age [11]. Chlorophyll amount indirectly estimates the nutrient status because much of leaf nitrogen is incorporated in chlorophyll [12]. In addition, leaf chlorophyll amount is closely related to plant stress [13].

The function of carotenoids in higher plants is influenced by where the pigments are synthesized. In chloroplasts, the two major roles of carotenoids are related to photosynthesis: light, harvesting, and protection from photo-oxidation [14,15]. The conjugated double bonds of carotenoids are responsible for their ability to adsorb photons in the visible wavelengths, and this property is essential to increase the spectrum of wavelength for light harvesting [14] The energy transfer from carotenoids to chlorophyll requires a close association [16].

This study examines the effects of leaf pigment contents (Chlorophyll a, b, and carotenoids) in two different seasons on pomegranates' plant-bearing healthy and cracked fruit. This study is vital as it affects photosynthesis and overall plant growth.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Sample Collection

This study was done with two variants of the same cultivar, bhagwa of pomegranate, in the Kachchh district of Gujarat state, India. Leaf samples of the same cultivar were collected from two different orchards, which were 1.5km apart from the same region. As the study examines pigment levels in healthy and cracked fruits, samples were collected from the orchard that contained almost all the nutritious fruits. In contrast, the selected second orchard contained plant-bearing cracked fruits. The geographical location of both orchards lies at 23°09'N latitude and 69°86'E longitude. The soils of the orchards were slightly alkaline and non-saline (pH 7.85 and EC 1.07 dS m⁻¹) and contained approximately 1.68% organic carbon. Fresh green leaves around the plant were collected in two seasons; the first season included a stage in which fruits were in the initial development stage (season 1), while in the second season, the fruits were at the ready-to-harvest stage (Season 2). Season 2 contained cracked fruits for the second orchard. Leaf sampling for the first season started on 14th August, and 25th January for season 2.

Pigment Study in leaves of Punica granatum L.

Accurately weigh 0.5g of fresh plant leaves of both the varieties of *Punica granatum L.* Using tissue homogenizer, the leaves were homogenized with 10 cm³ of different extracting solvents (95% ethanol, methanol, 80% acetone, and DMSO). The homogenized sample mixture was centrifuged for 15 minutes at 40°C at 10,000 rpm. The supernatant was isolated from the residue, and 1 ml of supernatant was diluted with 4 ml of the respective solvent [17-19]. Solutions were analyzed for Chlorophyll-a, Chlorophyll-b, and carotenoid content in a UV-Visile Spectrophotometer (Shimadzu). The concentration of pigments in various solvents was calculated from the following equations (Table 1).

The experiment was designed in a randomized complete block design with three replications. In each replication, one tree was used and collected at intervals of 5 days. Statistical analysis of all data was performed with SPSS,20 version. Differences between the means were compared, and analysis of variance (ANOVA) was carried out at a significance level of P<0.05.

Table 1. Calculation of magnitude of pigments concentration for various extracting Solvents

Extracting Solvent	Equations
95% Ethanol	Ch-a=13.36A664 – 5.19 A649 Ch-b=27.43A649 – 8.12 A664 Cx+c=(1000A470–2.13Ca-97.63Cb)/209
Methanol	Ch-a=16.72A665.2 – 9.16A652.4 Ch-b=34.09A652.4 – 15.28A665.2 C x+c=(1000A470 – 1.63Ca – 104.96Cb)/221
80% Acetone	Ch-a=12.25A663.2 – 279A646.8 Ch-b=21.5A646.8 – 5.1A663.2 C x+c=(1000A470– 1.82Ca –85.02Cb)/198
DMSO	Ch-a=12.47A665.1 – 3.62A649.1 Ch-b=25.06A649.1 – 6.5A665.1 C x+c=(1000A480– 1.29Ca-53.78Cb)/220

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The plant's photosynthetic activity is among the vital parameters that influence yield, and it can be detected by measuring leaf chlorophyll content and net photosynthetic rate [20]. For plants containing healthy fruits, during early development stage of fruit (Season 1) (Table 2.) average chl-a content was 8.073,11.518,12.513 and 15.810 mg/L, respectively, in various solvents. For plants containing cracked fruits, during season 1 average chl-a content was 8.671,10.686,12.734 and 17.505 mg/L during season 1. No drastic variation was observed in season-1 for both the varieties.

Table 2. Quantification of Chlorophyll a, Chlorophyll b, and Carotenoids (mg/L) in leaves of *Punica granatum L.* in various extracting solvents for (season -1)

Pigments	Leaves of Plant bearing Healthy fruit (Season -1)(ppm)				Leaves of Plant bearing Cracked fruit (Season -1)(ppm)			
	14/08	19/08	24/08	Average	14/08	19/08	24/08	Average
95% Ethanol								
Pigments	14/08	19/08	24/08	Average	14/08	19/08	24/08	Average
Chlorophyll a	8.519	8.2	7.5	8.073	9.913	8.3	7.8	8.671
Chlorophyll b	4.5	4.1	3.988	4.196	5.0	4.846	4.2	4.682
Carotenoids	2.340	1.8	1.2	1.780	2.116	2.0	1.5	1.872
Methanol								
Chlorophyll a	12.454	11.3	10.8	11.518	11.2	10.5	10.358	10.686
Chlorophyll b	1.116	1.1	1.0	1.072	1.7	1.2	1.441	1.447
Carotenoids	3.4	4.1	3.585	3.695	4.0	3.5	2.403	3.301
80% Acetone								
Chlorophyll a	12.0	14..219	11.5	12.573	11.87	13.902	12.5	12.734
Chlorophyll b	7.396	6.8	7.5	7.232	8.0	6.8	7.703	7.501.
Carotenoids	4.1	3.353	3.2	3.551	5.2	3.1	1.879	3.393
Dimethyl Sulphoxide (DMSO)								
Chlorophyll a	16.930	16.0	14.5	15.810	18.015	16.5	18	17.505
Chlorophyll b	9.0	11.930	8.5	9.810	10.5	10.0	12.232	11.244
Carotenoids	5.096	5.057	5.432	5.195	5.466	5.378	5.65	5.498

As Chlorophylls are essential pigments for photosynthesis. In green plants, chlorophyll is the primary pigment used in photosynthetic processes to transport light energy to a chemical acceptor [22]. The amount of chlorophyll varies in the leaves of higher plants as they go

through distinct developmental phases. For plants containing healthy fruits, average carotenoid content was 1.780, 3.695, 3.551, and 5.195 mg/L, respectively, in various solvents during the early development stage of fruit (season-1), and for plants containing cracked fruits, average chl-a content was 1.872,3.301,3.393 and 5.498 mg/L during season 1. As not much deviation was observed in pigments for both varieties, the photosynthetic rate is similar during the early development stage for both varieties.

Table 3. Quantification of Chlorophyll a, Chlorophyll b, and Carotenoids (mg/L) in leaves of *Punica granatum* L. in various extracting solvents for (season -2)

Pigments	Leaves of Plant bearing Healthy fruit (Season -2)(ppm)				Leaves of Plant-bearing Cracked fruit (Season -2)(ppm)			
	25/01	30/01	04/02	Average	25/01	30/01	04/02	Average
95% Ethanol								
Chlorophyll a	8.1	7.902	7.2	7.734	8.0	7.5	5.782	7.094
Chlorophyll b	3.497	2.8	2.1	2.799	2.5	1.660	2.2	2.120
Carotenoids	0.45	0.55	0.422	0.474	0.788	0.8	0.65	0.746
Methanol								
Chlorophyll a	11.873	11.2	10.8	11.291	11	9.5	11.363	10.621
Chlorophyll b	-0.2	-0.1	-0.564	-0.288	-0.715	-0.55	-0.85	-0.705
Carotenoids	2.8	2.2	1.744	2.248	3.1	2.1	1.703	2.301
80% Acetone								
Chlorophyll a	11.50	11.0	10.065	10.855	10.348	9.0	9.5	9.616
Chlorophyll b	5.8	6.1	4.498	5.466	3.138	3.258	4.35	3.582
Carotenoids	4.333	3.120	2.462	3.305	2.035	0.697	1.159	1.297
Dimethyl Sulphoxide (DMSO)								
Chlorophyll a	11.026	9.997	10.978	10.667	9.230	8.253	8.407	8.630
Chlorophyll b	6.097	5.329	6.025	5.817	5.195	4.458	3.892	4.515
Carotenoids	3.4	2.9	2.799	3.033	2.546	2.172	1.786	2.168

The average chl-a content for a plant containing healthy fruit during season 2 when fruits were in a ready-to-harvest state were 7.734, 11.291,10.855, and 10.667 mg/L, respectively, in various solvents. Similarly, the chl-a content for a plant containing almost all cracked fruits during season -2 was 7.09,10.621,9.616 and 8.630 mg/L in multiple solvents (Table 3). Thus, all chlorophyll parameters changed during the season. Both varieties' chl-a, chl-b, and carotenoid content were wide in early August (season 1). They decreased throughout development periods and reached the lowest level during harvest (season 2). A drastic decrease was observed in pigment content for plants containing cracked fruits during season 1 and season 2, indicating reduced photosynthetic activity from the early development stage to the matured stage.

Reduced photosynthesis results in a decrease in the number of accessible metabolites needed for plant growth. The crops' ability to photosynthesize is one of the critical elements affecting the yield that may be observed by physiological characteristics such as leaf chlorophyll concentration, net Stomatal conductance and photosynthetic rate [21]. This study examined the effect of leaf chlorophyll content in two different seasons for plants bearing healthy and cracked fruit.

Chl-b content showed a similar trend to chl-a. It was higher at the beginning than at the season's end (Table 2). The highest chl-b content, 9.810mg/L, was obtained from plants containing healthy fruit during season 1 in DMSO solvent. A drastic decrease in chl-b content was observed for both varieties during season 2 (Table 3).

Carotenoid content followed a similar trend as chl-a and chl-b. A drastic decrease was found in carotenoid content during season 2 for both varieties. Average carotenoid content

decreased to 0.474, 2.248, 3.305, and 3.033 mg/L, respectively, in various plant solvents containing healthy fruit during season 2 when fruit was ready to harvest. Similarly, carotenoid content also decreased for plants containing almost all cracked fruits during season -2, and it decreased to 0.746, 2.301, 1.297, and 2.168 mg/L, respectively, in various solvents (Table 3).

Fig. 1. Pigment levels in leaves of Pomegranate in 95% Ethanol in seasons 1 & 2

As shown in Fig. 1, Chlorophyll a, b, and carotenoid levels in leaves extracted with 95% ethanol declined significantly between Season 1 and Season 2 for both healthy and cracked fruits; more variation was observed for cracked fruits, suggesting reduced photosynthetic activity as fruits mature.

Fig. 2. Pigment levels in leaves of Pomegranate in 80% Acetone in seasons 1 & 2

In Fig. 2, pigment levels in 80% acetone show a similar trend to 95% ethanol with lower chlorophyll and carotenoid content as the season progresses, particularly in plants with cracked fruits

Fig. 3. Pigment levels in leaves of Pomegranate in DMSO in seasons 1 &2

The highest amount of chl a, b, and carotenoid levels were found in leaves extracted with DMSO solvent, indicating more extraction than acetone and ethanol (Fig 3). A similar trend, 95% ethanol and acetone, were followed with lower chlorophyll and carotenoid content as the fruit reached matured, particularly in plants with cracked fruits. From Fig1,2,3, it can be observed that pigment level decreases more in all extracting solvents for cracked fruits than healthy fruits, as the fruit reaches from early development stage to matured one, indicating a decrease in photosynthetic activity.

Table 4. Regression coefficient results from the data of experiments for pigment yield

Values	Mean	Std. Deviation	Coefficients	Standard error	t - value	p-value
Value of Pigment (mg/L) (Constant)	5.83	4.28	7.82	1.32	5.93	.000
Season	1.50	0.504	2.383	.508	4.691	.000
Health of the fruit	2.00	0.822	-.349	.311	-1.123	.265
Solvent	2.50	1.126	1.215	.227	5.348	.000
LevelPigments	2.00	0.822	-3.952	.311	-12.71	.000

Table 5. Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) for Pigment Study

SS	DF	f-value	P-value	Mean Square	R ²	Adjusted R ²
For Pigment Yield						
990.658	4	53.333	0.0010	247.664	0.761	0.747

SS: sum of squares; DF: Degree of Freedom

Leaf average chl-a, chl-b, and Carotenoids affected pomegranate's health (healthy and cracked fruit). These differences were statistically significant. Average leaf chl-a, chl-b, and total chlorophyll of plants containing healthy fruit were higher than that of plants containing healthy fruit during both seasons. The leaf chlorophyll content was the lowest at season 2 when fruits were in a matured state. The highest values were found during the early development stage for both varieties.

Leaf chlorophyll content was found to be lowest in cracked fruits during Season 2 (January-February, winter). Seasonal changes, particularly in summer and winter, influence both pomegranate fruit cracking and chlorophyll degradation. Cold winter conditions can slow metabolic activity, which delays chlorophyll degradation compared to warmer months [23]. Since the solar energy absorbed by a leaf largely depends on photosynthetic pigment levels, decreased chlorophyll content can directly impact photosynthetic efficiency and, ultimately, primary productivity [20].

According to [24], an increase in nutrient uptake from the roots correlates with higher leaf chlorophyll levels. Chlorophyll a, chlorophyll b, and total carotenoids were found to be higher in plants with healthy fruits in both seasons compared to those with cracked fruits. Both nutrient uptake and water availability are critical for maintaining fruit quality. A balanced nutrient management strategy, combined with adequate irrigation, helps minimize cracking and optimizes chlorophyll levels [25-26].

Increased pigment levels, particularly chlorophyll, have been shown to enhance photosynthetic efficiency, promoting improved growth and fruit yield [27]. Additionally, higher concentrations of anthocyanins and carotenoids in fruits contribute to their antioxidant properties, thereby enhancing fruit quality and shelf life [28]. Elevated pigment levels can also strengthen a plant's resistance to diseases, reducing the incidence of pests and pathogens [29]. Plants with higher pigment content tend better to withstand environmental stresses, such as drought or salinity, ensuring consistent productivity [30]. This aligns with our findings, as plants bearing healthy fruits exhibited higher pigment levels in both seasons than those with cracked fruits.

Studies have shown that DMSO frequently results in higher yields of pigments due to its strong hydrogen-bonding capabilities, which enhance the solubility of plant pigments and make the extraction process more efficient than many other organic solvents [31]. DMSO also does not denature proteins or other biological molecules, helping to preserve pigment integrity during extraction [32]. Its ability to effectively penetrate cell membranes facilitates the release of intracellular pigments [33].

According to Gallardo, cracking in olives results in a loss of green pigments and color degradation [34]. The enzyme chlorophyllase, which facilitates chlorophyll degradation, is more active in saline conditions. High levels of Na⁺ and Cl⁻ are likely contributors to the reduction of chlorophyll content in leaves [35]. Moran suggests that the nutrient status of a plant can be indirectly assessed by measuring chlorophyll content [36]. Low chlorophyll levels may indicate Fe deficiency or insufficient solar radiation penetration [37-38].

From the analysis of variance, the model for pigment levels was found to be highly significant ($p < 0.01$), with an R² (coefficient of determination) value of 0.761. This R² value indicates that 76.1% of the total variation in the observed response can be explained by the model or by the experimental parameters and their interactions. The remaining 23.9% of variation was not accounted for by the model (Table 5). The coefficient estimates in the regression model for pigment analysis are presented in Table 4.

CONCLUSION

The study concludes that leaf chlorophyll content is closely associated with plant stress and senescence. This experiment demonstrated that chlorophyll and carotenoid levels significantly impact the health of pomegranate trees. Notably, chlorophyll a, chlorophyll b, and carotenoid content showed a decline from early fruit development to the final, harvest-ready stages. The lowest chlorophyll levels were recorded in plants with cracked fruits, suggesting that chlorophyll quantification could serve as a valuable indicator of plant health. Additionally,

variations in chlorophyll a and b levels may provide insights into the incidence of fruit cracking in pomegranates, which may be mitigated by addressing specific contributing factors. Regular chlorophyll content analysis is recommended for assessing nutrient levels in pomegranates. Identifying and managing the parameters that reduce chlorophyll content in leaves could be crucial in preventing fruit cracking and minimizing economic losses for farmers.

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